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NOTES ON THE 2030 AGENDA FOR SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT: the importance of research on the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) in Brazil

APONTAMENTOS SOBRE AGENDA 2030 PARA O DESENVOLVIMENTO SUSTENTÁVEL: a importância de pesquisas sobre os Objetivos de Desenvolvimento Sustentável (ODS) no Brasil

NOTAS SOBRE LA AGENDA 2030 PARA EL DESARROLLO SOSTENIBLE: la importancia de la investigación sobre los Objetivos de Desarrollo Sostenible (ODS) en Brasil

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Abstract: The 2030 Agenda was launched by the United Nations in 2015 and consists of 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Its creators addressed issues of importance to different societies around the world. Brazil is a signatory to the 2030 Agenda, and Brazilian universities are crucial to achieving these goals. Therefore, it is crucial that educational and research institutions in the country expand and deepen their studies on the SDGs, especially to develop social technologies that are appropriate to Brazil's diverse territorial realities. Thus, the objective of this article is to reflect on the importance of conducting research on the 2030 Agenda and to present incipient ideas on potential social technologies. To achieve this objective, bibliographical research was conducted, and the ideas were inspired by Futures Studies.

Keywords: Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), social technologies, 2030 Agenda; territory.

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Resumo: A Agenda 2030 foi lançada pelas Nações Unidas no ano de 2015 e é composta por 17 Objetivos de Desenvolvimento Sustentável (ODS). Seus idealizadores se preocuparam com temas caros para as diferentes sociedades ao redor do mundo. O Brasil é signatário da Agenda 2030 e as universidades brasileiras são de suma importância para o cumprimento das metas. Deste modo, é de suma importância que as instituições de ensino e pesquisas no país passem a ampliar e aprofundar estudos sobre os ODS, em especial, para criar tecnologias sociais que sejam adequadas as diferentes realidades territoriais brasileiras. Deste modo, o objetivo deste artigo é refletir sobre a importância de realizar pesquisas sobre a Agenda 2030 e apresentar ideias incipientes sobre tecnologias sociais que podem ser produzidas. Para atingir o objetivo foi realizado pesquisa bibliográfica, além disso as ideias foram inspiradas nos Estudos de Futuro.

Palavras-chave: Objetivos de Desenvolvimento Sustentável (ODS), tecnologias sociais, Agenda 2030; território

Resumen: La Agenda 2030 fue lanzada por las Naciones Unidas en 2015 y está compuesta por 17 Objetivos de Desarrollo Sostenible (ODS). Sus creadores se preocuparon por cuestiones que eran importantes para diferentes sociedades alrededor del mundo. Brasil es signatario de la Agenda 2030 y las universidades brasileñas son de suma importancia para alcanzar estos objetivos. Por ello, es de suma importancia que las instituciones de educación e investigación del país comiencen a ampliar y profundizar los estudios sobre los ODS, especialmente para crear tecnologías sociales que se adapten a las diferentes realidades territoriales brasileñas. Así, el objetivo de este artículo es reflexionar sobre la importancia de realizar investigaciones sobre la Agenda 2030 y presentar ideas incipientes sobre las tecnologías sociales que se pueden producir. Para lograr el objetivo se realizó una investigación bibliográfica y las ideas se inspiraron en los Estudios de Futuro.

Palabras clave: Objetivos de Desarrollo Sostenible (ODS), tecnologías sociales, Agenda 2030; territorio.

INTRODUCTION

The "2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development" was adopted by all 193 Member States of the United Nations on September 25, 2015. The Agenda is "a comprehensive plan of action for people, planet, and prosperity" (UNITED NATIONS, 2015). It consists of

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17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), 169 targets, more than 230 indicators to measure progress, and a framework for monitoring and review.

The creators of the 2030 Agenda addressed issues of importance to different societies around the world, and the 17 universal Goals were developed based on important and widely discussed contemporary issues. These include the eradication of poverty (SDG 1); the fight against hunger (SDG 2); the promotion of well-being and healthy lives for all (SDG 3); the establishment of quality education (SDG 4); combating gender inequality (SDG 5); sustainable water management (SDG 6) and access and affordable energy for all (SDG 7); promoting decent work (SDG 8); fostering innovation and sustainable industrialization (SDG 9); reducing inequalities within and among countries (SDG 10); establishing inclusive and resilient cities (SDG 11); sustainable consumption and production (SDG 12); adopting measures to combat climate change (SDG 13), ocean conservation (SDG 14), sustainable protection/restoration/promotion of terrestrial ecosystems (SDG 15) and promoting peaceful and inclusive societies (SDG 16), as well as strengthening the means to promote sustainable development (SDG 17).

Brazil is a signatory to the 2030 Agenda, and therefore, Brazilian universities are crucial to achieving its goals. According to Leta et al. (2020), universities are responsible for generating innovative technologies, training qualified human resources, and transferring knowledge to the productive sector. These contributions are essential to boosting the national economy and promoting competitiveness in the global market.

Through their research, teaching, and service activities, they address key issues related to the seventeen SDGs. For Leal Filho et al. (2021), universities have the capacity to promote significant change by working in partnership with governments, businesses, and civil society.

In addition to contributing to the SDGs, Brazilian universities have a responsibility to actively participate in the creation of sustainable development policies. Through their research and expertise, they provide technical and scientific input to support the formulation of effective public policies. This interaction between academia and

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government is crucial for implementing sustainable strategies and achieving concrete results (ZAGONEL et. al., 2019).

How are different areas of knowledge in Brazil discussing the 2030 Agenda? How are undergraduate, master's, and PhD programs discussing the topic? How are the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) of the 2030 Agenda being addressed in Brazilian academic research?

These initial questions lead us to a problem that revolves around two axes:

1. The relationship between research in Brazilian academia and the Global Agenda involving sustainable development; and
2. Creating solutions for society based on research funded by funding agencies

This issue raises further questions: How do different areas of knowledge engage with the SDGs? How do they address issues such as ending poverty, food security, inclusive education, gender equality, sustainable water management, reliable energy access for all, the city as an inclusive and safe settlement, among other topics that are important to the 2030 agenda?

How is it possible to think, in light of the SDGs, about social technologies² (ITSBRASIL, 2022), such as analysis tools, inter-institutional communication and planning between academia, government and private sectors and different sectors of society based on research carried out at Brazilian universities?

These questions are extremely important, as they bring together three key elements of the contemporary world: 1) The university as a producer of knowledge, 2) science, and 3) the need for sustainable practices in the 21st century.

However, it will not be possible to answer these questions here. In this text, our intention is to highlight the importance of conducting research based on the theme "Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) of the 2030 Agenda" and to present incipient ideas on social technologies that can be produced.

2 Social Technology is the "Set of transformative techniques and methodologies, developed and/or applied in interaction with the population and appropriated by it, which represent solutions for social inclusion and improvement of living conditions" (ITSBRASIL, 2022).

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To achieve this objective, a bibliographical search was conducted, as well as the theoretical framework surrounding the SDGs and the 2030 Agenda, documents, and programs published by Brazilian planning agencies. In addition to the concept of "social technology," "territory" appears as a priority concept. "Territory" should be understood as a social context endowed with contradictions, endowed with and managed based on different uses, characteristics, conflicts, and specific demands (SANTOS and SILVEIRA, 2001). Furthermore, the ideas presented were inspired by Future Studies (FERGNANI, 2020) and are speculations about the future.

Thus, in addition to this introduction, the text is structured into two additional sections. The second section presents a set of ten reflections, containing some insights into the importance of the topic and research involving the 2030 Agenda. The final section will be reserved for concluding remarks.

SDGs, MULTIPLE RESEARCH PROJECTS, AND RESULTS: The Importance of the 2030 Agenda

THE IMPORTANCE OF RESEARCH ON THE TOPIC

Research on the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) is increasingly popular in Brazilian academia because 1) it is current and relevant in both the global and national contexts; 2) it is interdisciplinary; 3) it impacts public policymaking at the municipal and state levels; 4) it can provide a more nuanced perspective on local challenges and enable the creation of sustainable solutions through the development of social technologies; and 5) it demonstrates the commitment of Brazilian researchers and universities to the 2030 Agenda. Thus:

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1. Agenda 2030: Current and Relevant Debate in the Global and National Context.

The SDGs are part of an agenda that addresses important issues of paramount importance to all nations and societies, including poverty eradication, gender equality (in politics, the workplace, the family, etc.), excellence in management and access to healthcare, education, energy, and clean drinking water, as well as the right to the city, with the debate on democratic, safe, and sustainable cities.

Hence the importance of more in-depth research on how these goals are addressed in dissertations and theses produced in Brazilian graduate programs to determine how these issues are addressed in Brazilian municipalities and states, which can contribute to understanding the needs of different territories.

2. SDGs and Interdisciplinary Integration

Interdisciplinary integration in SDG research can mean exploring ways for different areas of knowledge to connect, both to update themselves as sciences and to contribute to an agenda that aims to present solutions to problems affecting the world as a whole, and especially the various regions of Brazil.

Research that generates solutions for the region can generate academic, economic, health and well-being, political, environmental, social, and cultural impacts. A focus on topics related to the 2030 Agenda can also help graduate programs in Brazil adapt to the new evaluation guidelines of the Coordination for the Improvement of Higher Education Personnel (CAPES), specifically in "Question 1," referring to the document "Common Guidelines for the Evaluation of Permanence of Stricto Sensu Graduate Programs."

Furthermore, it would mean aligning the identities of master's and doctoral programs with the goals of virtually all SDGs. Therefore, research intertwined with the

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SDGs and Brazilian scientific fields can contribute to addressing complex challenges and promoting integrated solutions.

3. **Agenda 2030 and Research: Public Policy Formulation at the Municipal and State Levels.**

Research on how dissertations and theses address the SDGs in Brazil can provide valuable insights and forecasts for the formulation of public policies that take territorial realities into account, based on the 2030 Agenda. Therefore, academic research can be a decisive factor in municipal governments' planning decisions.

Research, for example, can contribute to the creation of Plans and Programs for states and municipalities based on the debate on sustainable development, contributing, above all, to the creation of public policies for climate adaptation (a key concept of SDG 13), especially hybrid planning mechanisms, with institutional structures that can engage in dialogue at the municipal, state, and university levels. Fernandes (2025) referred to these institutions as Territorial Interactive Units (ITUs).

ITUs can be a "stage" for the institutionalization of MACAs, in other words, methodologies of analysis, communication, and action (MACAs). Evaluation methodologies would be applicable techniques for analyzing official documents, theses, dissertations, reports, etc., enabling the development of proactive instruments based on the 2030 Agenda goals, especially mitigation (and adaptation) strategies.

Regarding communication methodologies, they would be useful for creating tools that collaborate and can help improve institutional dialogues for creating and implementing policies. Such methodologies, combined with the Plans and Programs of the Federative Units and municipalities, could create mechanisms that promote interaction, in the planning sphere, between different state apparatuses and civil society actors..Sustainable awareness requires the expansion of democracy and, above all, the overcoming of conflicts between planning units. In fact, the intention would be to devise supranational dialogue mechanisms that contribute to international cooperation for

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development and enable the pursuit of exchanges and financing, based on mitigation and adaptation efforts carried out around the world.

Action methodologies are related to how knowledge is applied; therefore, clearly defined variables are required to materialize an idea. Hence, the intention is to structure programs and plans based on the concepts and goals of the 2030 Agenda to propose a method that takes into account Brazil's diverse territorial realities, institutional realities, and existing methodologies and strategies for promoting sustainable strategies.

4. Territory/2030 Agenda Relationship: Possibilities for Creating Sustainable Solutions at the Local Level

Research based on the SDGs can provide a more in-depth look at local challenges and can enable the creation of sustainable solutions through social technologies. Different Brazilian territories face specific challenges. Investigating how academic production addresses issues such as land and water use, environmental preservation, industrialization, and others in light of the SDGs can generate innovative and efficient solutions, such as:

- a) Spaces for deliberation on public policies;
- b) Territorial agencies for inter-institutional communication between universities, different social segments, and the private sector;
- c) Community fundraising units for resolving environmental issues and centers for training sustainable citizens;
- d) Territorial and community research units;
- e) Mobile units for presenting legislative proposals to society;
- f) Training courses for researchers, professors, professionals, workers, and other segments to seek sustainable solutions adapted to their social realities (including the use of new technologies, such as Artificial Intelligence), etc.

5. Brazilian Universities and the SDGs: Commitment to the 2030 Agenda.

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Research dedicated to topics related to the 2030 Agenda demonstrates the commitment of Brazilian researchers to contributing to a sustainable and inclusive world. It also demonstrates how Brazilian universities are aligned with global values of sustainable development and the Brazilian government's most recent efforts to eradicate poverty, combat hunger, promote the creation of green technologies, and meet the climate mitigation goals established in important conventions such as the Paris Agreement and the goals of each SDG.

THE IMPORTANCE OF RESEARCH BASED ON THE 2030 AGENDA

SDG-based research is relevant because: 1) it can contribute to strengthening graduate programs as tools for promoting sustainable development; 2) it can be useful in identifying thematic priorities for future investments; 3) it can enable the expansion of theoretical and methodological approaches and the internationalization of teaching and research institutions; 4) it can promote the spatial contextualization of different territories for the purpose of creating MACAs; and 5) it can contribute to the efforts of Brazil and its academic institutions in achieving the SDGs. Thus:

1. Tools for inducing sustainable development

Research based on the SDGs can contribute to the development and updating of different areas of knowledge in Brazil, as well as to reinforcing the importance of master's and doctoral programs as tools for inducing the development and production of green technologies³.

3 Understand green technology as a set of products, systems or equipment that mitigate the negative effects of human activities, whose objectives are to control climate change, protect the natural environment, reduce our dependence on non-renewable resources (such as fossil fuels) and remedy the damage caused to the environment (QAMAR et. al. 2021).

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Updating scientific fields, strengthening graduate programs, and developing green technologies can contribute to the advancement and enrichment of the academic field and scientific knowledge by updating important disciplinary debates in the training of individuals trained at Brazilian universities, adapting them to the new demands of the 21st century, and instrumentalizing Brazilian basic research.

2. Identifying thematic priorities

Research based on the SDGs can enable the analysis of territorial characteristics, which means revealing priorities for public agencies' actions. This process allows efforts to be directed to specific areas, enabling adaptations to the territorial reality, and the creation of diagnostics and inter-institutional planning tools between academia, other government agencies, and society. thus expanding democratic exercises in sustainable and inclusive cities.

3. Internationalization and New “Perspectives” and Practices

Academic analyses based on the 2030 Agenda can enable the creation of new methodologies and foster the internationalization of Brazilian teaching and research institutions.

Research conducted in light of the SDGs allows us to determine what types of theoretical and methodological approaches are currently being used by researchers around the world. They can also contribute to expanding the methodological repertoire, as such research requires interaction with the other theoretical and methodological frameworks that supported the creation of the 2030 Agenda.

Such interactions can promote innovation in national research and overcome the disciplinary conception of education. The disciplinary conception common to the Brazilian

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educational reality in many cases does not meet the perception of *backwardness* (SANTOS, 2016) of the communities that interact directly with their territories⁴.

Furthermore, research related to the SDGs can help Brazilian universities engage more intensely with the most current debates on theme-based research, which promote interactions between physicists and sociologists, biologists and historians, educators and mathematicians, etc., thus breaking the epistemological boundaries of traditional academic sciences (AGB-ALFENAS, 2022).

4. Analysis of Space and Different Realities

By promoting research that links the SDGs and territory, Brazilian universities can foster spatial contextualization at different scales (federal unit, municipality, neighborhood, street, residence, etc.).

Spatial contextualization can enable the creation of specific diagnoses tailored to local realities in different geographic regions (immediate and intermediate) (LOSCHI, M.; FERREIRA, D., 2017) for the development of methodologies and techniques for assessment, communication, and action (MACs), especially strategies in the field of climate mitigation, resilience, and adaptation⁵.

5. Brazil and the 2030 Agenda

Research based on the 2030 Agenda can contribute to Brazil's efforts to achieve the SDGs and create a more just world for this and future generations.

4 For Santos (2016), contemporary democracies should no longer be avant-garde, as the avant-garde is elitist, the result of a conception of academic and epistemological knowledge that disregards territorial realities. Policies must have a new epistemology, they must be rearguard, which means considering the dynamics of communities, their advances, their expectations, popular knowledge, and the temporalities of subjects.

5 Adaptation strategies attempt to "fix" or adapt territories to the effects of climate change. These are generally local and/or regional actions tailored to local realities. Climate mitigation actions, on the other hand, aim to combat the causes of climate change. These concepts are directly linked to SDG 13 of the 2030 Agenda (UNITED NATIONS, 2015).

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This represents a significant opportunity for academic institutions to contribute to the creation of social technologies aligned with the objectives and actions established by the current Brazilian government, which launched the "Global Alliance Against Hunger and Poverty" in November 2024 at the G20 Leaders' Summit in Rio de Janeiro. The Summit's final document, which contains the terms of the initiative launched by the current president, shows that the "Global Alliance" is directly linked to SDGs 1 and 2 and intersects with SDGs 3, 4, 5, 10, 12, 13, 14, 15, and 17.

Furthermore, the research can lead to the creation of ideas that implement Law No. 10,973/2004 (Innovation Law⁶, regulated by Decree 9,283/2018) and the actions outlined in the Ecological Transformation Plan (ETP) and the "Pact for Ecological Transformation."

Regarding the ETP, the Plan was launched by Finance Minister Fernando Haddad at the 2023 United Nations Climate Change Conference (COP28). This is a diplomatic tool that aims to reposition Brazil in the international system as a leader in the Global South, challenging established development paradigms. Furthermore, the proposal expresses the Global South's commitment to becoming a center for promoting a green economy and advocating for an environmentally and socially sustainable and inclusive global context (MINISTRY OF FINANCE, 2023).

The PTE has six axes of action: 1) Sustainable finance; 2) Technological densification of the productive sector; 3) Bioeconomy and agri-food systems; 4) Energy transition; 5) Circular economy; and 6) Infrastructure and adaptation to climate change. The objectives are to generate employment and increase productivity, promote social justice and environmental sustainability in Brazil (MINISTRY OF FINANCE, 2023b). On the other hand, the "Pact for Ecological Transformation" is a document that establishes a commitment between the Executive, Legislative, and Judicial branches of the Brazilian State to act in an integrated and harmonious manner to promote ecological

6 The law deals with incentives for innovation and scientific and technological research in the production environment.

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transformation in Brazil, based on actions divided into three axes: Axis I: territorial and land use planning; Axis II: energy transition; Axis III: sustainable development with social, environmental, and climate justice.

Furthermore, the actions will be developed based on twenty-six measures to achieve five general objectives: 1) ecological sustainability; 2) sustainable economic development; 3) social, environmental, and climate justice; 4) consideration of the rights of children and future generations; and 5) resilience to extreme weather events. The actions outlined in the Pact, launched by the Brazilian government in August 2024, are globally aligned with the PTE (MINISTRY OF FINANCE, 2024).

Furthermore, this is a topic and research of current global interest, the results of which can help Brazil implement a series of policies based on the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), as well as contribute to other efforts to reverse Brazil's negative SDG performance. The Report of the Civil Society Working Group for the 2030 Agenda, published in 2022, revealed that the country has regressed in 65% of the 169 established targets.

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

Several societies are discussing the SDGs. Research projects on this topic in Brazil could contribute to Brazil's continued engagement in these debates, the creation of an international network that enables technological exchanges and training for Brazilian researchers, and the creation of sustainable development strategies tailored to the Brazilian reality, thus contributing to the creation of effective development strategies aligned with the realities of Brazilian municipalities.

Research on the SDGs can contribute to the creation of a set of social technologies, green technologies, assessment, communication, and action methodologies, and special MACAs to renew the relationship between scientific knowledge and territorial realities.

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Research on the SDGs could generate results that can contribute to other ongoing efforts aimed at strengthening scientific and academic production in the country, creating opportunities for continued studies aimed at creating solutions that respond to current local and global challenges. Furthermore, it can contribute to a deeper understanding of how other research addresses the SDGs, which means stimulating reflections that could result in innovation initiatives in different geographic regions. It can also foster partnerships (national and international) and the development of further research aimed at promoting social, environmental, and economic sustainability.

Such research can further consolidate the University's role in generating applicable knowledge and help impact Brazil's socioeconomic development. Furthermore, it can contribute to contemporary discussions about the implementation of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), an issue that is on the agenda and widely discussed internationally.

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